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The Method of Art Therapy as a Correction of Emotional Stress in the Younger Generation

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***Abstract:** The article is devoted to the problem of studying preschool stress. The results of diagnostics of the peculiarities of stress development in younger schoolchildren are presented. Based on the survey, the attitude towards the severity and causes of stress of schoolchildren, teachers and parents was revealed. The possibilities of art therapy as a method of stress correction in the younger generation are analyzed.*

***Key words:** stress, correction, art therapy, emotional stress, prevention of anxiety.*

Introduction. In recent years, art therapy has become an increasingly popular method of treatment and rehabilitation in various fields of medicine, including dentistry. Art therapy is a special type of therapy based on the use of artistic materials and methods to achieve the psychological and physical well-being of the patient. In dentistry, art therapy can be used to reduce stress and anxiety in patients associated with dental visits, as well as to assist in rehabilitation after various procedures. One way to use art therapy in dentistry is to create drawings or another artwork before or during a dental visit. This can help patients focus on the creative process and take their mind off worries before the procedure. Studies show that art therapy can significantly improve the psychological state of patients before visiting the dentist and help them cope with pain and discomfort after the procedures.

In addition, art therapy improves communication between the dentist and the patient, which increases the effectiveness of treatment. The dynamic development of modern civilization has its negative sides. One of them is the increasing stress of our lives. The ongoing pandemic has also contributed to an increase in stress levels in all categories of the population. But there is a category of people who are especially vulnerable to stress and its negative consequences – these are children, teenagers and young people. Stress is particularly dangerous for them due to the fact that they do not have the knowledge and experience to cope with stress and have not yet sufficiently developed psychological defense mechanisms. It is known that the greatest danger is not so much severe as prolonged, chronic stress.

This is associated with the danger of chronic school stress for students, the importance of its timely prevention and effective correction of consequences. School stress can cause maladaptation conditions in children, expressed in passivity, self-doubt, and a sense of inadequacy. It can lead to depression, alienation, negativism towards other people and society as a whole, compensatory aggression, which in extreme cases can underlie such socially dangerous phenomena as bullying, joking, and exposure to extremist ideology. Compensatory aggression can easily be redirected to other national and religious groups, giving rise to extremism and terrorism. Of course, these are extreme cases. And in most cases, school stress and related maladaptation interfere with the full disclosure of creative potential and self-realization of the individual. This can lead in the future to school maladjustment, which blocks motivation and activity for years, and the development of a student's capabilities.

Results and discussions. Stress is an emotional state that occurs in response to any requirement for the body and is expressed in the mobilization of resources to meet this requirement. Accordingly, school stress is generated by the requirements imposed on the student by the process of school education. School stress is defined as difficult situations that arise in the education system in which a student does not have sufficient resources to solve them, and which may threaten his mental and physical safety. In cases where it becomes chronic, school stress leads to overspending of resources and exhaustion of the child. Psychoemotional stress is a type of emotional state that is characterized by increased physiological and mental activity, and one of its main characteristics is extreme instability. In adverse conditions, stress can transform into a state of nervous and emotional tension, which is characterized by a decrease in the efficiency and effectiveness of functioning of systems and organs, and most importantly – a rapid depletion of the body's energy resources. As experience shows, art therapy can significantly improve the psychological state of patients before visiting the dentist and help them cope with pain and discomfort after the procedures. In addition, art therapy improves communication between the doctor and the patient, which increases the effectiveness of treatment. One of the most effective means of dealing with emotional stress in children is regular visual arts classes. Visual arts and drama therapy, both passive (contemplation, experiencing the phenomena of art) and active (creation of works of art), are not only a means of aesthetic influence, but also help the individual to build an adequate system of psychological protection. Artistic activity provides an opportunity for everyone to feel like a creator, to learn how to compensate for negative experiences by means of art, to model the communicative process both in communicating with their own works and in interacting with other people in the process of collective creative activity. In the process of visual activity, favorable conditions are also created for the development of an emotionally positive perception of art, which, in turn, contributes to the formation of a positive aesthetic attitude to reality. The essence of the psychoanalytic approach in art therapy is to provide an opportunity for a person to realize their problems through the products of their own creativity. This is considered not only necessary, but also sufficient to overcome them. (*Figure 1*)

Figure 1. How children imagine toothache

The psychoanalytic approach does not imply the possession of practical skills of artistic expression. It follows from this that an individual is able to consciously and actively perceive himself and others, change something in himself, and not only be a slave to circumstances, that is, change something in the reality around him, and not just adapt to it. It is obvious that art therapy constructs an inner world of experiences, safe risks, and solvable problems, offering first to draw paintings, make engravings, installations, theatrical productions and photographs, or sculpt from clay, and then project the products of their creativity into everyday life. Working with the means of artistic expression, including color, learning their nature and method of application, a person in the process of creative activity finds solutions to accumulated problems, acquires the ability to independently design his own life. In our country, art therapy works with at-risk adolescents, the disabled, victims of terrorist acts, etc. began relatively recently, about 10-15 years ago. Programs are being developed in which various projects are proposed. To carry out art therapy work, specialists need deeper knowledge and skills in various types of artistic activity. We have developed an art therapy program for corrective work with stress and its negative emotional consequences. Art therapy - treatment with art or creativity has always been considered one of the most effective methods of correcting psychoemotional conditions. After all, a person's need to express their emotions, feelings and mood is one of the sources of creativity. Drawing, like any creative activity, relieves psycho-emotional stress. Art therapy is a field of psychotherapy that involves the creation and analysis of creative works. Methods of art therapy, for example, drawing therapy aimed at awareness, experiencing and overcoming negative emotions, and the formation of a positive attitude through visual means, is another method of mastering one's own mental states. The most common art therapy practice is isotherapy as a type of art therapy based on drawing, pictorial activity to create it. By painting, a person gives vent to his feelings, desires, dreams, rebuilds his relationships in various situations and painfully comes into contact with some frightening, unpleasant, traumatic images. (*Figure 2*)

Figure 2. The vision and expression of the feelings of teenagers towards today's dentistry

Drawing acts as a way of comprehending one's capabilities and the surrounding reality, as a way of modeling relationships and expressing various kinds of emotions, including negative, negative ones, therefore, drawing is widely used to relieve mental tension, stressful states, when correcting neuroses, fears. Drawing is a means of relieving tension by returning to primitive forms of functioning and satisfying unconscious desires. The work contributes to the repression, the breakthrough of the content of complexes into consciousness and the experience of the negative emotions accompanying them. This is especially important for those who cannot "talk it out", it is easier to express their fantasies in creativity than to talk about them. Such methods contribute to the projection of one's inner self to express thoughts and feelings. Art therapy helps the child to demonstrate non-standard thinking, their experiences, hidden problems, and emotional background. Such therapies allow him to be alone with himself, thus helping to find inner harmony. And it is used in work even with very young children. This method helps to cope with fears, anxiety, and many psychosomatic manifestations. And, in the end, creativity allows you to enjoy self-expression. In addition, the fact that you have created something yourself helps to increase self-esteem, forms an idea of yourself as a person; creates a positive self-perception. The very process of drawing teaches the child to concentrate on his feelings and feelings, to be aware of his emotions, and to express them; moreover, to express negative emotions in an adequate form.

Art therapy expands their opportunities for self-expression and communication with an adult about their experiences. There are many different approaches to conducting art therapy: identifying yourself with what you are drawing; drawing without intention, following your hand, drawing what she wants; "collective drawing": a method that is especially effective at the initial stages of learning, as it helps to unite the team and establish trust between them.

It is very important to note that this technique has no contraindications and limitations. Art therapy gives anyone the opportunity to express their inner world through creativity

Conclusion. Thus, given the importance of this problem and the danger of its consequences, knowledge of methods of prevention and reduction of school anxiety should be one of the requirements for the training of future educational personnel. Art therapy is an effective method of reducing stress and anxiety in patients of dental clinics. It helps to improve communication between the dentist and the patient, as well as create a more pleasant atmosphere during treatment. The use of art therapy in dentistry can significantly improve the quality of care and patient satisfaction. The development of this area in dentistry can lead to a reduction in stress in patients and an increase in the success of therapeutic manipulations. Awareness of your emotions, coping with them often becomes a problem for many. Art therapy allows you to use creativity to realize, live and express your emotions and feelings.

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